

contrast, the di-ortho-substituted-anisoles (6-10) show decreased electron density (downfield shift) compared with anisole. These chemical shifts leave no doubt regarding the existence of SER in 2-5 and steric inhibition of resonance in 6-10 (Table 1).

The above view gets further support from the structural parameters (Table 2) obtained for substituted anisic acids from crystallographic measurements⁶. The shortening of the C₁-O bond and the increase in the C₁-O-CH₃ angle of the mono-substituted-t-Bu compound (2) compared with unsubstituted anisic acid (1; Table 2) indicate enhancement of resonance in it. The lengthening of the C₁-O bond and the decrease in C₁-O-CH₃ angle in the 2,6-disubstituted compounds (3-5; Table 2) compared with anisic acid indicate steric inhibition of resonance in them. Increased resonance (SER) of the methoxyl increases the double bond character of the C₁-O bond and shortens the bond; the C₁-O-CH₃ bond angle also increases due to increased sp² hybridisation of the σ-bonding electrons of oxygen. Decreased resonance increases the C₁-O bond length and decreases the C₁-O-CH₃ angle.

Schuster *et al.*⁵ used the data (Tables 1 and 2) for a different purpose. They made no reference to steric enhancement of resonance in 2-alkylanisoles.

TABLE 2—SELECTED STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS* OF SUBSTITUTED-ANISIC ACIDS*

Compd. no.	Substituent	C ₁ -OCH ₃ bond length	O-CH ₃ bond length	C ₁ -O-CH ₃ angle degrees
		Å	Å	
1	R ₁ =R ₂ =H	1.356	1.435	118.1
2	R ₁ =t-Bu, R ₂ =H	1.347	1.445	120.8
3	R ₁ =R ₂ =Me	1.381	1.417	115.5
4	R ₁ =R ₂ =i-Pr	1.388	1.425	114.0
5	R ₁ =R ₂ =t-Bu	1.374	1.424	116.5

*Data from Ref. 5.

tited anisic acids from crystallographic measurements⁶. The shortening of the C₁-O bond and the increase in the C₁-O-CH₃ angle of the mono-substituted-t-Bu compound (2) compared with unsubstituted anisic acid (1; Table 2) indicate enhancement of resonance in it. The lengthening of the C₁-O bond and the decrease in C₁-O-CH₃ angle in the 2,6-disubstituted compounds (3-5; Table 2) compared with anisic acid indicate steric inhibition of resonance in them. Increased resonance (SER) of the methoxyl increases the double bond character of the C₁-O bond and shortens the bond; the C₁-O-CH₃ bond angle also increases due to increased sp² hybridisation of the σ-bonding electrons of oxygen. Decreased resonance increases the C₁-O bond length and decreases the C₁-O-CH₃ angle.

Schuster *et al.*⁵ used the data (Tables 1 and 2) for a different purpose. They made no reference to steric enhancement of resonance in 2-alkylanisoles.

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Negative Ion Mass Spectra of Coumarin Derivatives†

K. P. MADHUSUDANAN*, VIJAI LAKSHMI, F. A. HUSSAINI and A. SHOEB

Medicinal Chemistry Division, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

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IDENTIFICATION and structure elucidation of coumarins are done with the aid of spectral techniques. The mass spectral fragmentation patterns of coumarins and related compounds have been reviewed¹⁻⁴. Metastable and collisional activation spectra have also been used for the differentiation of isomeric coumarins². However, there are only a very few reports on the negative ion mass spectra

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TABLE 1—ION ABUNDANCES (%) IN NICI (CH₄) AND NICI (Cl⁻) SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS 1–12

Compd. no.	NICI (CH ₄)			NICI (Cl ⁻)			
	M ⁻	(M-H) ⁻	(M-Me) ⁻	(M+Cl) ⁻	M ⁻	(M-H) ⁻	(M-Me) ⁻
1	202 (100)	201 (77)	—	237 (43)	—	201 (100)	—
2	232 (35)	231 (24)	217 (100)	267 (100)	—	231 (54)	217 (34)
3	246 (30)	—	231 (100)	—	—	—	231 (100)
4	246 (18)	—	231 (100)	281 (1)	246 (10)	—	231 (100)
5	290 (19)	—	275 (100)	325 (97)	—	—	275 (100)
6	290 (3)	—	275 (100)	325 (100)	—	—	275 (24)
7	308 (1)	—	293 (100)	343 (100)	—	—	293 (11)
8	296 (100)	—	—	331 (55)	296 (100)	295 (28)	—
9	326 (100)	—	311 (65)	361 (7)	326 (100)	325 (27)	311 (23)
10	328 (100)	327 (12)	—	—	—	327 (100)	—
11	380 (100)	379 (16)	—	415 (13)	—	379 (100)	—
12	544 (85)	529 (100)	257 ^a (17)	579 (5)	—	—	307 ^b (100)

^a(RDA-Me)⁻. ^b(RDA+Cl)⁻

of these compounds³. Generally negative ion mass spectra are simple giving only fewer peaks than their positive ion counterparts. Several coumarin derivatives have been isolated from plant sources in our laboratory⁴ and many have been found to possess marked biological activity. An examination of the negative ion chemical ionisation (NICI) mass spectra of these compounds (1–12) revealed that negative ion mass spectrometry is a very sensitive technique which gives information not only about the molecular weight but also about the nature of the substituents with trace quantities of the material. The results of our study are presented in this note.

Experimental

The NICI spectra were recorded on a Jeol D-300 mass spectrometer. The ion source conditions were: electron energy, 200 eV; emission current, 300 μA; temperature 200°. The electron capture spectra were recorded using CH₄ and the NICI (Cl⁻) spectra were recorded using a mixture CHCl₃/MeOH (1 : 10) as the reagent gases.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the ion abundances in the NICI (CH₄) and NICI (Cl⁻) spectra of compounds 1–12. The presence of an α,β-unsaturated carbonyl function enables the molecules to accommodate the captured electron. The only fragment ions observed in the spectra correspond to losses of H or Me radical from the aromatic OH and OMe groups present in the molecule. For example, the hydroxy compounds (1, 2, 10 and 11) give abundant (M-H)⁻ ions, while the methoxy compounds (2, 3–7, 9 and 12) show

intense peaks corresponding to loss of Me from the M⁻. 8-Hydroxy-5-methoxypsoralen (2) which contains both OH and OMe groups show (M-H)⁻ and (M-OMe)⁻ ions. In compounds 5–7, the presence of the side-chain does not affect the fragmentation pattern. The base peak in the positive ion electron impact spectrum of toddasin (12) corresponds to the RDA fragment at *m/z* 272. However, in its negative ion spectrum the only evidence for the formation of this fragment is the minor ion at *m/z* 257 corresponding to loss of Me from the ion at *m/z* 272.

The ion abundances in the NICI (Cl⁻) spectra are also given in Table 1. Chloride adduct ions are abundant in compounds in which hydrogen bonding of Cl⁻ is possible. In such cases M⁻ ions are not prominent though (M-H)⁻ and (M-Me)⁻ ions are observed in aromatic OH and OMe containing derivatives. However in 8 and 9, electron capture is the predominant process owing to the extended conjugation possible in these molecules. The (M+Cl)⁻ ions are not stable in 10 and 11 presumably due to the facile loss of HCl leading to abundant (M-H)⁻ ions. In 12 the abundant ion at *m/z* 307 corresponds to the chloride adduct of the RDA fragment. Its abundance was found to vary with the ion source and probe temperature indicating that the RDA fragment is produced by thermal decomposition of the molecule prior to ionisation.

A recent report by Blom⁵ describes the estimation of elemental composition using moment analysis. In this technique the composition of the ion is determined from the moment of the isotopic distribution by comparing the calculated moment and that obtained from the abundances of the isotopic peaks in the spectra. As these coumarin derivatives

give abundant $(M+Cl)^-$, M^- and $(M-Me)^-$ ions this technique was applied to these molecules. A few representative results from this analysis is given in Table 2. The results indicate that because of the simplicity, negative ion spectra of these compounds are ideal for finding their elemental compositions using moment analysis.

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION FROM MOMENT ANALYSIS

Compd. no.	Ion	Composition	Deviation of moment
2	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{12}H_8O_5Cl$	-0.0212
	M^-	$C_{12}H_8O_5$	0.0122
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{11}H_6O_5$	-0.0043
4	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5Cl$	-0.0191
	M^-	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5$	0.66
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{12}H_7O_5$	-0.0088
5	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{16}H_{18}O_5Cl$	-0.0302
	M^-	$C_{16}H_{18}O_5$	-0.0351
	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{15}H_{16}O_5$	0.0117
6	$(M-Me)^-$	$C_{15}H_{16}O_5$	-0.0087
7	$(M+Cl)^-$	$C_{16}H_{20}O_5Cl$	-0.0005
8	M^-	$C_{15}H_{20}O_5$	0.0087

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Molecular Rearrangement. IV. Oxidation Products of Acetoxyaleuritic Acid Methyl Ester and Molecular Rearrangement of its Epoxide

JAYANTA BANERJEE^a, GITALI DUTTA^a, U. K. SOM^b,
K. E. HAQUE^c and C. P. DUTTA^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

^bGovernment Quinine Factory, Mungpoo, Darjeeling
^cInstitute of Pharmacy, Kalyani-741 235

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IN continuation of our investigations¹ on the molecular rearrangement involving epoxide ring opening in pentacyclic triterpenoid skeleton, olean-14-en-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl acetate (1) was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid whence in addition to the desired epoxide olean-14 α ,15 α -oxido-28-carbomethoxy-3 β -yl-acetate (2), $C_{33}H_{52}O_5$, (M^+ , 528), m.p. 176–78°, two other interesting rearranged products, compounds (A) and (B) were isolated. The α -orientation of the epoxy function in 2 was justifiable from both pmr studies and mechanistic consideration. The mass spectra of 2 indicated the fragmentation pattern in agreement with that of olean type of triterpenoids².

Compound-A, $C_{33}H_{52}O_5$ (M^+ , 528), m.p. 190–92°, showed ir absorption bands at 3540 and 830 cm^{-1} attributable to a hydroxyl and a trisubstituted double bond. The carbonyl bands for ester and the acetate group appeared at 1740 and 1745 cm^{-1} as twin peaks. Pmr spectrum showed a overlapping multiplets in the region δ 0.8–1.16 which were assigned to seven tertiary-methyl groups and an ill-defined triplet at δ 5.36–5.44 (1H) due to olefinic proton at C_{12} . The low field shift of C_{18} -methine proton at δ 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, J 4 Hz) was attributable due to allylic double bond at C_{12-13} and anisotropic effect of 28-carbomethoxy group. A one-proton double doublet at δ 4.02–4.20 ($J \sim 11$ and 5 Hz) after D_2O exchange suggested the presence of 15 β -axial proton in the molecule. The multiplicity of the downfield signal around δ 5.24–5.36 of the C_{15} -methine proton bearing the acetoxy function of the diacetate (4) also corroborated the presence of β -axial proton at C_{15} and thereby indicating the presence of a α -equatorial OH group at C_{15} . The formation of C_{15} - α -equatorial hydroxy group therefore confirmed the α -orientation of the epoxide since the configuration around C_{15} remains unaffected during opening of the epoxide ring. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern and the above spectral data identified the compound-A as olean-12-en-28-carbomethoxy-15 α -hydroxy-3 β -yl acetate (3). Besides the molecular ion peak at m/z 528, other significant fragmentations at m/z 249 and 219 (M^+ –250–59, 100%) were formed by retro-Diels-Alder cleavage of ring-C.

In conformity with the structure (3) compound-A upon acetylation with Ac_2O /pyridine furnished the